

Condensed 1,8-Naphthyridines. Part-4. Synthesis of 7-Arylbenzimidazo[1',2':1,6]pyrimido[4,5-b][1,8] naphthyridines

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7-Arylbenzimidazo[1',2':1,6]pyrimido[4,5-b][1,8]naphthyridines (VI) have been prepared by the oxidation of 7-aryl-6,7-dihydrobenzimidazo[1',2':1,6]pyrimido[4,5-b][1,8]naphthyridines (IV). The dihydro compounds (IV) have been obtained by the condensation of benzaldehydes with 2-amino-3-(2-benzimidazolyl)-1,8-naphthyridine (III) which in turn obtained by the condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (I) with 2-cyanomethylbenzimidazole (II). The structures of the compounds have been established by elemental analyses and spectral data.

IN continuation of our earlier reports on the synthesis of 2-substituted¹⁻³ and 2,3-fused 1,8-naphthyridines⁴⁻⁶, we describe in this paper the synthesis of hitherto unreported 7-arylbenzimidazo[1',2':1,6]pyrimido[4,5-b][1,8]naphthyridines. 1,8-Naphthyridines with heterocyclic system fused at 2,3-positions exhibit a variety of biological activities⁷⁻¹⁴. The synthetic approach to the title compounds is outlined in Scheme 1.

2-amino-3-(2-benzimidazolyl)-1,8-naphthyridine (III) in good yield. The structure assignment of III was based on its elemental analysis and ir, proton nmr and mass spectral data. The ir spectrum of III showed strong peaks at 3140 and 3420 cm⁻¹ confirming the presence of benzimidazole-NH¹⁵ and amino function on the 1,8-naphthyridine framework, respectively. In the proton nmr spectrum of III, (DMSO-d₆ + CDCl₃) the signal at δ 2.45, 3.80

Scheme 1

The condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (I) with 2-cyanomethylbenzimidazole (II) in the presence of ethanol with a trace of piperidine gives

and 8.70 are due to the presence of two protons of NH₂ group, one proton of NH (benzimidazole moiety), and the C-7 proton on naphthyridine¹⁶

framework, respectively. The protons at C-4, C-5 and C-6 resonated along with four aromatic protons as a complex multiplet at 7.0-8.4. The mass spectrum of III showed strong peaks at m/z 261 (M^+ , 100%), 260 ($M^+ - H$, 26), 245 ($M^+ - NH_2$, 60), 236 ($M^+ - C_2H_5$, 13), 234 ($M^+ - HCN$, 11), 219 ($M^+ - NH_2 - C_2H_5$, 5), 208 ($M^+ - C_2H_5 - HCN$, 20), 171 (5), 144 (5), 143 (8), 118 (9) and 90 (12).

Condensation products of III with aromatic aldehydes in the presence of glacial acetic acid can be either Schiff bases, 2-benzalamino-3-(2-benzimidazolyl)-1,8-naphthyridines (V) or the isomeric 7-aryl-6,7-dihydrobenzimidazo [1',2' : 1,6] pyrimido [4,5-*b*] [1,8] naphthyridines (IV). The selective formation of IV is in this context explained on the basis of the ir spectra. In the ir spectra, the absence of the characteristic broad band of hydrogen on benzimidazole (3140 cm^{-1}) indicates the condensation products to be the cyclic dihydro system IV. Physical data of these compounds are given in Table 1.

The dihydronaphthyridines (IV) were smoothly oxidised by $KMnO_4$ in glacial acetic acid to 7-arylbenzimidazo[1',2':1,6]pyrimido[4,5-*b*][1,8]naphthyridines (VI), which showed the absence of NH group in the ir spectra. The mass spectrum

of 7-*p*-chlorophenyl VI showed prominent peaks at m/z 381 (M^+ , 25%), 299 (8), 287 (60), 277 (10), 261 (100), 246 (30), 245 (80), 244 (40), 235 (10), 218 (5) and 217 (10). Physical data of these compounds are recorded in Table 2.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected. The purity of all the compounds was checked by tlc. Ir spectra (nujol) were run on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer, proton nmr spectra on a Varian EM-390, 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as the internal references, and the mass spectra on a Varian MAT CH-7 instrument at 70 eV.

2-Amino-3-(2-benzimidazolyl)-1,8-naphthyridine (III): A mixture of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (I, 0.1 mol) and 2-cyanomethylbenzimidazole (II, 0.1 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (20 ml) in the presence of a catalytic amount of piperidine for 0.5 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and the solid thus obtained was filtered. The product was crystallised from dimethylformamide as pale yellow crystals (95%). m.p. $>300^\circ$ (Found: C, 69.00; H, 4.25; N, 26.91. $C_{15}H_{11}N_5$ requires C, 68.96; H, 4.21; N, 26.82%).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 7-ARYL-6,7-DIHYDROBENZIMIDAZO[1',2':1,6]PYRIMIDO[4,5-*b*][1,8]NAPHTHYRIDINES (IV)

Sl. No.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
1.	Phenyl	>300	80	$C_{22}H_{18}N_5$	75.71 (75.64)	4.30 (4.29)	20.23 (20.05)
2.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	>300	72	$C_{22}H_{17}N_5O$	72.91 (72.82)	4.91 (4.48)	18.35 (18.47)
3.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	>300	76	$C_{22}H_{17}N_5$	76.15 (76.03)	4.70 (4.68)	19.30 (19.38)
4.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	>300	80	$C_{22}H_{14}N_5Cl$	68.85 (68.83)	3.70 (3.65)	18.21 (18.25)
5.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	>300	80	$C_{22}H_{14}N_5Br$	61.71 (61.68)	3.30 (3.27)	16.40 (16.35)
6.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	>300	80	$C_{22}H_{14}N_5O_2$	67.15 (67.00)	3.40 (3.55)	21.36 (21.31)
7.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	>300	85	$C_{22}H_{14}N_5O_2$	67.92 (67.00)	3.62 (3.55)	21.29 (21.31)
8.	2-Thienyl	>300	60	$C_{20}H_{12}N_5S$	67.58 (67.60)	3.70 (3.66)	19.69 (19.71)

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF 7-ARYLBENZIMIDAZO[1',2':1,6]PYRIMIDO[4,5-*b*][1,8]NAPHTHYRIDINES (VI)

Sl. No.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
1.	Phenyl	>300	40	$C_{22}H_{18}N_5$	75.98 (76.08)	3.69 (3.74)	20.20 (20.17)
2.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	>300	40	$C_{22}H_{18}N_5O$	73.19 (73.20)	3.90 (3.97)	18.60 (18.56)
3.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	>300	35	$C_{22}H_{18}N_5$	76.50 (76.45)	4.10 (4.15)	19.40 (19.39)
4.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	>300	40	$C_{22}H_{15}N_5Cl$	69.11 (69.01)	3.18 (3.13)	18.28 (18.30)
5.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	>300	40	$C_{22}H_{15}N_5Br$	62.00 (61.97)	2.74 (2.80)	16.40 (16.43)
6.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	>300	40	$C_{22}H_{15}N_5O_2$	67.40 (67.34)	3.10 (3.02)	21.50 (21.42)
7.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	>300	40	$C_{22}H_{15}N_5O_2$	67.40 (67.34)	2.99 (3.02)	21.45 (21.42)
8.	2-Thienyl	>300	35	$C_{20}H_{12}N_5S$	68.10 (67.98)	3.14 (3.11)	19.70 (19.83)

General procedure for preparation of 7-aryl-6,7-dihydrobenzimidazo[1',2' : 1,6]pyrimido[4,5-b][1,8]naphthyridines (IV): 2-Amino-3-(2-benzimidazolyl)-1,8-naphthyridine (III, 0.1 mol) and aromatic aldehyde (0.1 mol) were refluxed in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) for 2 h. The resulting solution was allowed to cool and poured onto crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered and crystallised from dimethylformamide to give IV.

7-Arylbenzimidazo [1', 2' : 1,6] pyrimido [4,5-b] [1,8] naphthyridines (VI) from IV : To a solution of IV (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml), finely powdered KMnO_4 (3.0 g) was added. The reaction mixture was heated on a steam bath for 0.5 h. It was then filtered while hot and clear filtrate was digested with hot water (200 ml). The rapidly separated solid was filtered and crystallised from aqueous dimethylformamide to give VI.

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